

ROLE OF EDUCATION IN PEACE BUILDING, CONFLICT RESOLUTION AND SOCIAL COHESION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Nigeria comprises numerous multi-ethnic communities characterized by diverse ethnic groups, cultures, and religions. Ethnicity, culture, and religion significantly influence the behavior of individuals within these communities. Differences in these aspects often render certain actions unacceptable to others, resulting in violence and conflict. Education serves as a key mechanism for promoting understanding and tolerance among individuals in multi-ethnic settings. Accordingly, this article critically examines the role of education in peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion in Nigeria. The structure of the paper includes an introduction, a review of the concepts of education, peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion, followed by an analysis of education as a means of fostering these outcomes. Subsequently, the challenges facing education in fostering peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion in contemporary Nigeria were discussed. Education contributes to cultural and religious tolerance, character development, acquisition of critical thinking skills, respect for fundamental rights and freedoms and addressing the root causes of grievances for promoting peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. Challenges to education's role in fostering peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion in contemporary Nigeria include inadequate funding, infrastructural decay, insufficient staffing, corruption, low staff motivation, data shortages, and ethnic, cultural, and religious diversity. Recommendations include increasing budgetary allocations to the education sector and motivating staff through improved salaries and allowances to enhance the implementation of educational programmes that promote peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion.

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1. Introduction

The contemporary Nigerian society is a multi-ethnic community, and the identity crisis resulting from differences in ethnicity, culture and religion threatens peaceful existence and leads to conflict that undermines the social cohesion of members of the society. Modupe (2025) opined that Nigeria is seriously threatened by ethnic, religious, and political diversities. The author added that in a plural society like Nigeria, the need for peace building, conflict resolution, and social

cohesion cannot be overemphasized in light of the myriad problems facing the country as a result of its heterogeneous nature. Similarly, Okorn and Anam (2026) asserted that Nigeria continues to experience diverse and persistent conflicts, including ethno-religious violence, farmer–herder disputes, separatist agitations, resource-based crises, urban criminality, and violent extremism. Furthermore, Okorn and Anam stressed that these conflicts have significantly undermined peace, social cohesion, economic development, and political stability across the country's regions. The difference between people living in multi-ethnic communities is inevitable but can be managed through education. Therefore, in a multiethnic state, one of the ways to build peace, foster conflict resolution and social cohesion is through education.

Education imparts essential knowledge and fosters attitudes, values, and behaviors necessary for building and maintaining harmonious relationships within society. Accordingly, this paper examines the role of education in peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion in Nigeria. The paper is organized into several sections: an introduction; a review of the concepts of education, peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion; an analysis of the role of education in these areas; a discussion of the challenges facing education in fostering peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion in contemporary Nigeria; and, finally, the conclusion and recommendations.

2. Conceptual Clarifications

This section clarifies key concepts to prevent misinterpretation and enhance understanding within the context of this study.

2.1 Concept of Education

Education is a teaching and learning activity geared toward training the mind, shaping character and enriching individuals' knowledge. Alikor and Okachiku-Agbaraeke (2025) described education as a deliberate process of inculcating individuals into social life through the transmission of knowledge, the acquisition of relevant skills, and the moulding of character by accepting a value system through formal and informal social agencies. Education enables individuals to develop the critical thinking skills required to solve personal and societal problems, create wealth, and improve their standard of living. Ossai (2023) defined education as an intentional and purposeful activity geared toward producing knowledgeable individuals who can think wisely and contribute to a sustainable community.

Education is a learning activity that equips individuals with the skills and knowledge needed to engage in productive endeavours and contribute meaningfully to society's progress. Eze (2024) defined education as the process by which a society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another. Furthermore, Eze argued that education is a process through which persons are trained to develop their innate potential so that it can be fully expressed externally. Adamu, Abubakar and Raji (2025) noted that education is the deliberate process through which a society equips its members with the knowledge, values, skills, and habits needed for both personal fulfillment and collective progress.

Education is a learning process through which individuals are exposed to the requisite skills and knowledge that liberate them from ignorance and enhance their self-reliance. Afshaneh (2023) defined education as the process of providing individuals with the skills and knowledge they need

to make informed decisions and to participate in the development of society. Nsude and Okenwa (2020) described education as the process of transmitting societal norms, values and desirable attitudes from one generation to another. Furthermore, Nsude and Okenwa asserted that education equips individuals with knowledge, abilities, skills and other forms of behavior to enable them to function well in their immediate environment and the society at large. Education is defined by Ibrahim and Aminu (2024) as the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes through various forms of learning such as instruction, study, or practical experience. Contextually, education is a process through which individuals are exposed to learning experiences to improve their knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

2.2 Concept of Peace building

Peace building is the deliberate effort to strengthen and maintain harmony in society. Peace building is any action aimed at developing and maintaining cordial relationships among people in society. Sa'idu and Adebayo (2026) described peace building as coordinated actions by stakeholders to de-escalate tensions, restore order, and create an environment conducive to unity and development. Peace building is the engagement of people in diplomatic interactions to maintain amity before, during, or even after conflict. According to Effendi and Ali (2026), peace building involves establishing and restoring relationships between or among aggrieved parties. The authors added that peace-building approaches involve reconstruction, rebuilding, rehabilitation, reconciliation, and reintegration.

Peace-building is concerned with establishing sustainable harmony to foster a serene atmosphere in society. Riak and Bill (2022) described peace building as an activity that aims to resolve injustice in non-violent ways among people of a given society. The authors added that peace building revolves around developing constructive, cordial relationships among people across ethnic, religious, class, national, and racial boundaries. According to Okogbule and Brown (2023), peace building is an intervention designed to prevent the onset or resumption of violent conflict by fostering sustainable harmony.

Peace-building is the process of creating conditions to enhance or restore unhealthy relationships among members of a society. Ukiyedeikimie (2023) noted that peace building encompasses all efforts to sustain pre-conflict and post-conflict peace. According to Mohammed (2025), peace building consists of a wide range of activities associated with capacity building, reconciliation, and societal transformation, and is a long-term process that occurs after a violent conflict has subsided. Furthermore, Mohammed stated that peace building also involves addressing the root causes of the conflict and creating long-term actions for sustainable harmony. Peace-building is the act of solidifying cordial relationships to prevent violence in society.

2.3 Concept of Conflict Resolution

Conflict resolution is the process of managing grievances and restoring harmony among the parties involved in a dispute. According to Sa'idu and Adebayo (2026), conflict resolution encompasses the systematic processes, strategies, and mechanisms designed to address conflicts and transform antagonistic relationships into peaceful coexistence. The authors added that conflict resolution refers to the process of addressing, managing, and resolving disputes or disagreements between two or more parties constructively and peacefully. Sekibo, Opeye, and Ojo (2025) defined

conflict resolution as the use of processes, tools and skills to address disagreements and disputes in a constructive and respectful manner.

Conflict resolution is the process of reaching an amicable agreement that satisfies all parties involved in a dispute. Afshaneh (2023) defined conflict resolution as the process of settling disputes or disagreements between two or more parties. The author added that it involves using various methods, such as negotiation, mediation, and arbitration, to reach a mutually beneficial agreement. Similarly, Edeh, Okwueze, Asoya, Leke, Atuluku and Ejigbo (2026) noted that conflict resolution involves a range of approaches, including negotiation (direct dialogue between parties), mediation (involvement of a neutral third party), arbitration (binding decision by a third party), facilitation (guiding group processes) and conflict transformation (changing underlying social structures). Conflict resolution is the act of settling grievances to promote cordial relationship among parties involved in disputes or misunderstanding.

2.4 Concept of Social Cohesion

Social cohesion is the existence of harmonious relationships among members of a given society. According to Danyaro and Muhammad (2026), social cohesion is the strength of relationships and the sense of solidarity among community members. Furthermore, Danyaro and Muhammad maintained that social cohesion involves shared values, trust, participation in communal activities, and the capacity to resolve conflicts peacefully. Okorie (2026) defined social cohesion as the level of trust, solidarity, collective identity and inclusion in the society. Furthermore, Okorie posited that social cohesion is a dynamic, situation-related process through which individuals and groups develop mutual trust, shared civic identity, fair participation and institutional legitimacy to maintain peaceful coexistence and common well-being within a particular society.

Social cohesion is the exhibition of togetherness among individuals residing in a given community or society. Jekayinoluwa and Adeowu (2026) viewed social cohesion as the level of confidence, mutual respect, partnership, and sense of inclusion experienced amongst members of a community. Chia and Abdulsamad (2025) referred to social cohesion as the bonds and relationships that bring people together in society. The authors added that it involves creating a sense of belonging, promoting trust, and fostering positive interactions between individuals and groups. Social cohesion strengthens solidarity and cooperation among members of a given community. Chan, To, and Chan (2021) defined social cohesion as the level of connectedness and solidarity among groups within society, emphasizing trust, shared values, and a desire to cooperate. Social cohesion is the presence of a unified community and shared values that encourage collaborative activities in a society.

3. Role of Education in Peace Building, Conflict Resolution and Social Cohesion.

Education serves as a means of fostering understanding and promoting cultural and religious tolerance, thereby enhancing peace building, conflict management, and social cohesion in society. Specifically, education promotes religious tolerance, which is essential for unity and peace building among community members. Afshaneh (2023) argued that education can be a powerful tool for peace building by promoting tolerance and understanding of diverse cultures and beliefs. By reducing misconceptions and increasing understanding of various religions, beliefs,

and practices, education enhances peace building, conflict management, and social cohesion. Yemi and Chianen (2024) emphasized that education plays a pivotal role in promoting social cohesion by fostering understanding, tolerance, and a sense of shared identity among individuals from diverse backgrounds. Additionally, education provides opportunities for interaction and learning among people from different ethnic, religious, and cultural backgrounds, thereby breaking down barriers and promoting social cohesion.

Education contributes to character development, enabling individuals to exhibit behaviors aligned with societal norms and values, which in turn enhances peace building and social cohesion. John and Ohanyiri (2025) argued that education facilitates the learning of ethics, guiding individuals to act in accordance with the cherished values and ideals of society, thereby promoting peace building and cohesion. Education also encourages the adoption of shared values such as harmony and unity. Dolia and Parihar (2025) asserted that education plays a transformative role in shaping, sustaining, and uplifting societal values and norms, making it a significant factor in peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. They further noted that education instills values such as truth, justice, compassion, equality, and responsibility, which constitute the moral foundation of peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. By teaching shared values and a sense of common humanity, education unites individuals to enhance peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. Yemi and Chianen (2024) emphasized that by nurturing a shared national identity and promoting unity and solidarity, education serves as a powerful tool for fostering social cohesion and inclusivity.

Education equips individuals with critical thinking skills necessary to evaluate and understand diverse perspectives and to engage in constructive dialogue, thereby fostering peace building and conflict resolution. It provides opportunities to approach issues from various cultural perspectives and belief systems, which is essential for resolving conflicts, building peace, and promoting cohesion in society. Yemi and Chianen (2024) argued that education enables individuals to recognize and appreciate the beliefs, practices, and values of others, facilitating more amicable conflict resolution and enhancing peace building and social cohesion.

Education fosters respect for fundamental rights and individual freedoms, thereby promoting peace building within society. It raises awareness of human rights and instills values such as fairness and justice, which are essential for peace building. Naik and Naik (2018) argued that effective education increases citizens' awareness of values such as self-determination, justice, dignity of life, public welfare, and harmonious coexistence, enabling them to adapt and contribute to peace building and cohesion. Furthermore, Naik and Naik noted that education enhances awareness of rights and duties, guides individuals when their rights are violated, and thus supports conflict resolution and social cohesion. Education also serves as a tool for promoting respect for cultural, political, and social differences, further fostering peace building and social cohesion.

Education equips individuals with the knowledge necessary to address the root causes of grievances or disputes, thereby promoting peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. Afshaneh (2023) argued that education provides the skills needed to understand the origins of conflict and to develop peaceful resolution strategies. The author further noted that education fosters an environment conducive to dialogue and understanding and can challenge structures of

power and inequality that contribute to conflict. Education also mitigates disputes arising from religious differences and addresses historical grievances and social intolerance. Yemi and Chianen (2024) stated that education plays a vital role in addressing historical grievances and promoting reconciliation by providing a platform for accurate historical education, dialogue, and healing past divisions, thereby enhancing conflict resolution and peace building. Education enriches knowledge and empowers individuals to approach conflict resolution from a peace-oriented perspective.

4. Challenges of Education in Fostering Peace Building, Conflict Resolution and Social Cohesion in Contemporary Nigeria

Poor funding of education is a setback to fostering peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion in contemporary Nigeria. Eze (2024) noted that budgetary allocation to education sector in Nigeria revealed that in 2021, 2022, 2019, 2018, 2017, 2016, 2015, 2014, 2013, 2012, 2011 and 2010 the percentage of total budget allocated to education sector were 5.14%, 5.13%, 5.86%, 5.94%, 6.12%, 6.65%, 9.26%, 9.04%, 8.68%, 8.55%, 7.88% and 6.17%. These percentages were far below the 26% of the annual budgetary allocation recommended by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) for education. Funds allocated to the education sector are insufficient to implement programmes that can foster peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. Poor funding stifles research, training initiatives, and staff motivation in learning institutions, hindering the implementation of educational programmes that promote peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion.

Infrastructural decay in educational institutions poses a threat to the implementation of educational programmes that can strengthen peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion in Nigeria. Many educational institutions have insufficient facilities and those that are available are in deplorable condition, adversely affecting teaching and learning activities that could promote peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. Ibrahim and Aminu (2024) posited that it is common to find that in most government schools, primary, secondary, and even university classrooms, workshops, seats, books, and requisite equipment are grossly inadequate. Also, Tseveda, Terzungwe, Sombo and Ogunode (2024) stressed that many tertiary institutions' faculties and departments of peace and conflict studies in Nigeria lack adequate lecture halls, laboratories and offices for both academic and non-academic staff. The authors added that the lack of these facilities affects the implementation of the curriculum of peace and conflict resolution. Adamu, Abubakar and Raji (2025) asserted that in an institution where there are no adequate classrooms, resource rooms, staff rooms, and a lack of laboratory facilities, computers, and the like, proper teaching and learning cannot be effective and efficient in fostering peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion.

Strike actions in learning institutions affect the effective implementation of educational programmes designed to promote peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion. Tseveda et al (2024) stated that many students have lost learning hours in their universities because of strike actions by the Academic Staff Union of Universities, ASUU, the Senior Staff Association of Nigerian Universities, SSANU, and Non-Academic Staff Union of Educational and Associated Institutions, NASU and the National Association of Academic Technologists (NAAT). At the secondary school level, academic activities that promote peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion are disrupted by strike actions by the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT).

Otakpo Louis and Brown (2024) asserted that during strike actions, academic activities are put on hold, and when students resume classes, there is often a rush of learning activities that can prevent them from acquiring knowledge of peace building.

Educational programmes that can foster peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion suffer several drawbacks due to corruption. This problem of corruption is also evident in educational institutions, where funds allocated to running school programmes are embezzled by government officials, education managers, and teachers. Adamu, Abubakar and Raji (2025) noted that funds budgeted for capital projects in the educational sector are diverted for personal use. Corruption can prevent the award of contracts and the recruitment of competent staff to effectively implement education programmes that foster peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion.

Many educational institutions have insufficient qualified staff to implement programmes that foster peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion. Adamu, Abubakar and Raji (2025) noted that the inadequacy of qualified staff negatively impacts the overall quality of education delivery in Nigerian learning institutions. Similarly, Tsevenda, Terzungwe, Sombo and Ogunode (2024) asserted that inadequate academic staff in education institutions is one of the problems militating against effective implementation of curricula that promote peace building, conflict resolution and cohesion.

Poor motivation of staff and educational managers demoralizes them from working hard to implement school programmes designed to strengthen peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion in Nigeria. Poor salaries of education workers affect their motivation to work hard in learning institutions. Adamu, Abubakar and Raji (2025) asserted that poor salaries, lack of housing (security), and general poor conditions of service by the government demoralize staff in learning institutions, leading to a lack of commitment to their duties in implementing educational programmes.

The shortage of data poses a serious threat to the planning and implementation of educational programmes that can enhance and strengthen peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion in Nigeria. Eze (2024) asserted that the absence of rudimentary data impedes the development of effective education planning, monitoring, programming, and policy-making to promote peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion in Nigeria. Shortage of data hinders effective planning of facilities, staff, and programmes, which hampers teaching and learning activities that can enhance peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion in Nigeria.

The problem of ethnic, cultural, and religious diversity affects the acceptance of education as a tool for peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion in Nigeria. People of a particular religion, ethnicity and culture have a strong belief system that can be easily changed through education.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, education is a powerful tool for building peace, resolving conflict, and promoting social cohesion. In Nigeria, education contributes to these outcomes by fostering

cultural and religious tolerance, shaping character, developing critical thinking skills, and encouraging respect for fundamental rights and freedoms. However, the effectiveness of education in these roles is undermined by challenges such as underfunding, infrastructural decay, staff shortages, and corruption.

6. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

1. Federal and State Governments should increase budgetary allocations to the education sector to facilitate the implementation of programmes that promote peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion.
2. Federal and State Governments should recruit and deploy qualified staff to support the implementation of educational curricula designed to strengthen peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion.
3. The Federal Ministry of Education should develop a national database for education statistics and make the information accessible through an online portal to facilitate planning and implementation of educational programmes to enhance peace building, conflict resolution and social cohesion.
4. Federal and State Governments should motivate staff through salary and other allowances to boost their morale and encourage them to work hard to implement educational programmes designed to enhance peace building, conflict resolution, and social cohesion.

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